

From intent to impact: Investigating the effects of open sharing commitments

Executive Summary

Prepared on behalf of Wellcome, UK Research and Innovation
and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

About this research

Read the full report at:
doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6620854

Read the Joint Statement at:
bit.ly/OpenSharingStatement

Download the evidence package at:
zenodo.org/communities/data-sharing-in-public-health-emergencies

In January 2020, Wellcome coordinated the issuing of a Joint Statement that called on researchers, journal publishers, and funders to ensure that research findings and data relevant to the COVID-19 outbreak are shared rapidly and openly to inform the public health response and help save lives. The Joint Statement was informed by the approach taken during the Zika and Ebola outbreaks, where similar statements were released.

Wellcome, UK Research and Innovation and The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation commissioned this research to understand the extent to which the commitments made by the various stakeholders were put into practice, and to determine the downstream impacts (if any) which arose as a consequence.

This research was jointly delivered by Research Consulting and Science-Metrix, via a mix of desk research, key informant interviews, an online survey and a bibliometric analysis. A full report, a technical annex and supporting research data are available to download via the Zenodo repository.

Gathering support for the Joint Statement

A total of 160 organisations signed the Joint Statement: signatories include research funders, research performing organisations, publishers and journals, learned societies and learned society publishers, preprint servers and more. The Statement required signatories to commit to the following:

All peer-reviewed research publications relevant to the outbreak are made immediately open access, or freely available at least for the duration of the outbreak.

Research findings relevant to the outbreak are shared immediately with the WHO upon journal submission, by the journal and with author knowledge.

Research findings are made available via preprint servers or other platforms before peer review and journal publication, with clear statements on data availability.

Researchers share interim and final research data relating to the outbreak, together with protocols and standards used to collect the data, as rapidly and widely as possible.

Authors are clear that data or preprints shared ahead of submission will not pre-empt its publication in journals.

Interviewees described the Joint Statements as “the right thing to do” in order to save lives in a global pandemic. In most cases, the Joint Statement helped shape the specific actions taken by signatories to respond to statement commitments, rather than affecting their overall attitudes to open sharing/open research.

The top three drivers for organisational signature were that:

- the Joint Statement was in line with existing organisational efforts around COVID-19;
- the Joint Statement helped signal alignment with open sharing practices to peer organisations; and
- the Joint Statement was useful as a focal point to drive discussions around open research.

Implementing Joint Statement commitments

The implementation of Joint Statement commitments took different shapes across signatory organisations. For example, publishers created new workflows to identify and share COVID-19 literature, while some funders introduced dedicated requirements in COVID-19 calls. Some signatories also referred to existing policies, where these were already in line with Joint Statement commitments.

COVID-19 portals

COVID-19 portals hosted by publishers or journals provided a single access point to relevant peer reviewed literature.

Automated tracking

Publishers designed new workflows, for example by adding tags or keywords in their manuscript tracking systems.

New mandates

Some funders updated their policies for dedicated COVID-19 calls, including specific terms in line with the Joint Statement's commitments

Waived article processing charges

Some publishers went beyond the Joint Statement commitments and waived article processing charges for publications relevant to the pandemic.

The monitoring of the commitments was limited across the board, and compliance mechanisms weren't in place for either research funders or publishers: there were no consequences from these organisations if relevant researchers for example did not share their data, include appropriate data availability statements or did not preprint their research. The lack of monitoring mechanisms also constrained this study's ability to fully assess the impact of the Joint Statement, and is a key opportunity for improvement for future statements.

Using bibliometrics to assess practice change

Shifting research cultures mean that it is more difficult to assess whether signatories have made changes due to the Joint Statement or because of other phenomena in the research landscape. The difference-in-differences approach used by Science-Metrix is key to address the extent to which any changes seen in signatory organisations may be tied to the Joint Statement.

of COVID-19 publications with signatory funding support had a preprint too

Preprinting is not universal practice

There was a clear increase in preprinting for signatory publications. This increase is larger than the increase seen for non-signatory publications. The majority of COVID-19 publications were not shared as preprints, indicating that the practice is still not widespread.

of COVID-19 publications with signatory funding support had a policy citation

Policy uptake was higher for signatory publications

Signatory COVID-19 publications benefitted from a greater increase in policy-related uptake across the board compared against pre-pandemic signatory publications. Non-signatory publications also tended to record increases, but these were smaller than for signatory publications.

of COVID-19 publications with signatory funding support were free to read

Publishers removed paywalls during the pandemic

A greater number of COVID-19 publications have been made available to read freely by signatories than by non-signatories. In particular, publisher-based free-to-read publications have seen an increase that can be linked back to one of the Joint Statement commitments.

of COVID-19 publications with signatory funding support had a DAS

Data sharing behaviours were difficult to assess

Although descriptive statistics did show increases around data availability statements (DAS) and data deposit, these could not be clearly attributed to the Joint Statement, and we note that overall levels of data sharing remain low across the board.

The long-term effects of open sharing statements

Some exceptional behaviours will return to normal

In the fast-evolving context of the pandemic, exceptional behaviours emerged, and the global research community refocused its efforts. Some of these behaviours are likely to “return to normal” after the pandemic (e.g. fast peer review, removal of paywalls), but practices such as preprint posting may well be here to stay given the extent of growth seen.

Commitments supporting open research are likely to continue

Signatory contributors acknowledged that their commitment to open research and open sharing is likely to continue in the future. Efforts to pursue open sharing will only work if the broader research landscape is aligned, particularly with regard to data sharing and preprinting, and these considerations will also affect the extent to which the world is prepared for a future pandemic.

Organisational workflows can be re-deployed in the future

Joint Statement signatories have devised a wide range of strategic and operational changes to implement their responses to COVID-19 in line with the commitments made. The Joint Statement may therefore positively affect a range of scenarios where signatories re-deploy such procedures to ramp up open sharing efforts and tackle a shared challenge.

Reflecting on the 2016 Zika Statement

COVID-19 Statement signatories encompassed a much larger proportion of research compared to the Zika Statement, and also led to impacts of larger magnitudes than those of the Zika Statement: it appears uncertain whether the latter can provide insight into the longevity of the former. While the Zika Statement has seen limited effects and longevity, this does not preclude that the COVID-19 Statement will have a different outcome in the medium- or long-term.

The impact of open sharing

This research indicated that open and rapid sharing was a key success factor in the global pandemic response, alongside efforts to collaborate internationally and the availability of advanced research infrastructures. In particular, open sharing of genomic viral data allowed the prompt development of vaccines, and the broader availability of publications and preprints helped inform policy in real time. Interviewees highlighted that the Joint Statement was useful to align the efforts of key stakeholders; influence their policy requirements and organisational targets during the pandemic (and, potentially, beyond); and shape the long-term vision for open research.

Opportunities for improvement

Joint Statement signatories fell short of their commitments to help ensure that “research findings are made available via preprint servers before journal publication” and that “researchers share interim and final research data relating to the outbreak”. Although descriptive bibliometric findings paint a positive picture of incremental gains in open sharing practices, there remains significant room for improvement and closer alignment with the behaviours that signatories committed to. In addition, the link between improvements in open sharing and the Joint Statement was difficult to establish, because there was no pre-existing monitoring framework for signatories and it is complex to disentangle closely related phenomena during a fast-evolving pandemic.

Key enablers

The success of the Joint Statement was underpinned by four key factors:

Brand recognition

Wellcome is a recognised and credible organisation, which conferred an extent of authority and prestige on the Joint Statement.

Track record

Wellcome was behind a previous statement released during the Zika outbreak. This also provided an initial set of possible signatories.

Timeliness

The Joint Statement was released at the right point in time, very early on in the pandemic and before other initiatives emerged.

Shared ethos

Signatories already sought to support the global pandemic response: the commitments in the Joint Statement were in line with this objective.

Recommendations for future statements

As noted above, some of the objectives in the Joint Statement were not achieved by signatories. This indicates that, while successful in several aspects, the Joint Statement could have been more effective in communicating clear operational targets to the cohort of signatories.

The impact, reach and inclusiveness of future initiatives can be maximised by considering the recommendations on the following page and building on the experiences of the Zika, Ebola and COVID-19 statements.

These recommendations will help the research and public health communities achieve more concerted and equitable outcomes at the international level and enhance the chances of a prompt resolution to future global crises.

1. Stronger expectations

The Joint Statement was effective in increasing access to publications and ensuring they were shared with the WHO. Given the demonstrable value of these practices, future statements should include strengthened expectations on data sharing and preprint posting, with clear guidance on how these should be achieved.

2. Assessment framework

This research was based on a post-hoc assessment framework developed two years after the Joint Statement's publication. Future statements should be accompanied (either immediately or within a matter of weeks) by an overview of their intended impact in the short, medium and long term (theory of change) and a range of success factors to be used for self-auditing purposes.

3. Operational guidance

The Joint Statement has been signed by a very diverse cohort, and its commitments are described broadly and not tailored to different actors. To support signatories, an accompanying guidance document should be provided with more detailed suggestions on the operationalisation of commitments, including tailored advice for different types of organisations.

4. Knowledge sharing

Building on recommendation 3, knowledge sharing mechanisms should be established to share operationalisation examples and enable signatories to learn from each other's experiences and challenges: this will allow signatories to more easily align with their commitments. It should be clearly communicated that a one-size-fits-all approach is unlikely to be successful.

5. Long-term impact

The Joint Statement led to an increase in free-to-read materials and a net differential loss of share in Gold OA by signatories. Free-to-read materials may be placed behind paywalls at any point: as a result, the impact of the Joint Statement on open sharing cultures may remain limited to the context of the pandemic rather than continue in the future.

6. Global equity

Open research can be more easily leveraged by high-income countries. As a result, the benefits arising from the implementation of the Joint Statement are liable to be reaped asymmetrically, with low- and middle-income countries not equally incentivised to share information. Future statements should explicitly foster equity in data sharing and reuse.

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Consulting team

Research Consulting is a mission-driven research and scholarly communication consultancy, working with national and international organisations to help them make the most of their research processes and findings. We are active participants in the research ecosystem, and our work covers all aspects of the research life-cycle.

Science-Metrix (an Elsevier company) is a recognised leader in the assessment of S&T policy and activities using bibliometric methods. We work for international government, educational, non-profit or private organizations that perform scientific research or are involved with research funding and management.

Any questions?

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Project sponsors

Wellcome supports science to solve the urgent health challenges facing everyone. Wellcome supports discovery research into life, health and wellbeing, and are taking on three worldwide health challenges: mental health, global heating and infectious diseases.

UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) is the largest public funder of research and innovation in the UK, with a budget of around £8bn. It is composed of seven disciplinary research councils, Innovate UK and Research England. UKRI operates across the whole country and works with its many partners in higher education, research organisations businesses, government, and charities.

The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation works to help all people lead healthy, productive lives. In developing countries, it focuses on improving people's health and giving them the chance to lift themselves out of hunger and extreme poverty. In the United States, it seeks to ensure that all people – especially those with the fewest resources – have access to the opportunities they need to succeed in school and life.